

Statistical review of
Clinical Outcomes and Plasma Concentrations of Baloxavir Marboxil and Favipiravir in COVID-19 Patients: An Exploratory Randomized, Controlled Trial

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The following review has been prepared in collaboration with members of the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership¹. The reviewers named above, and other, unnamed discussants of the paper, are all qualified statisticians with experience in clinical trials. Our objective is to provide a rapid review of publications, preprints and protocols from clinical trials of COVID-19 treatments, independent of journal specific review processes. We aim to provide timely, constructive, focused, clear advice aimed at improving both the research outputs under review, as well as future studies. Given our collective expertise (clinical trial statistics) our reviews focus on the designs of the trials and other statistical content (methods, presentation and accuracy of results, inferences). This review reflects the expert opinions of the named authors, and does not imply endorsement by the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership, its wider membership, or any other organization.

Here we review *Clinical Outcomes and Plasma Concentrations of Baloxavir Marboxil and Favipiravir in COVID-19 Patients: An Exploratory Randomized, Controlled Trial* by Lou *et al*², uploaded on MedRxiv on the 5th of May 2020.

Overall, this was a small (n = 30) exploratory RCT that was not appropriately powered to reliably detect minimally useful treatment effects, and thus the trial can't say much about the potential usefulness of the treatments being tested, one way or the other. The results on the blood concentrations of the treatments might be useful for understanding appropriate dosing.

Study Summary

The paper reports an exploratory, open-label trial with three arms involving 30 adults hospitalized with qRT-PCR confirmed COVID-19, from February 3, 2020, in Zhejiang, China. Patients were randomly allocated in a 1:1:1 ratio to receive one of the following three treatment regimens: standard antiviral treatment (which consisted of inhaled interferon- α , and either lopinavir/ritonavir or darunavir/cobicistat and arbidol); standard antiviral treatment plus baloxavir marboxil (80mg orally on days 1 and 4 and a third dose on day 7 if still SARS-CoV-2 positive); or standard antiviral treatment plus favipiravir (initial dose of 1600 mg or 2200mg orally, followed by 600 mg three times a day for up to 14 days). The primary outcomes were the percentage of subjects that were SARS-CoV-2 negative by day 14 post-randomization, and the time from randomization to clinical improvement, measured as hospital discharge, or a 2 point improvement on a seven category ordinal scale ranging from *not hospitalized with resumption of normal activities* to *death*. Secondary outcomes were SARS-CoV-2 negativity by day 7; and ICU admission, need for mechanical ventilation, and mortality by day 14. Viral loads, drug concentrations, and clinical presentations were also observed.

In a per-protocol analysis of 29/30 patients, the percentage of patients who were negative for SARS-CoV-2 after 14-days post-randomization was 70%, 77%, and 100% in the baloxavir marboxil, favipiravir, and control groups, respectively; while the respective median times to clinical improvement were 14, 14 and 15 days. The authors reported no other meaningful differences between the groups, and concluded that their findings didn't support the addition of either baloxavir marboxil or favipiravir to existing antiviral treatment. The authors did not conduct any statistical tests or use any other inferential methods, which they justified based on the exploratory nature of the study.

We sincerely thank the authors for their contribution to our collective understanding of COVID-19, for their commitment to the timely dissemination of research results.

Major comments

The study was too small to draw any conclusions one way or another.

This is a small exploratory trial with no sample size calculation. For this reason, the authors avoided the use of any statistical tests or other inferential methods, which was a reasonable decision in our opinion. However, the authors still discuss the results in terms of treatment efficacy, despite the study being underpowered for any reasonable treatment effects and not reporting the degree of uncertainty in any estimated effects.

Recommendations:

For future studies

- Follow guidance for the design and reporting of pilot and feasibility studies, or collaborate with other researchers to design an appropriately powered efficacy trial.

For this study

- Consider adding confidence intervals to convey the uncertainty in treatment effects.
- Avoid referring to treatment efficacy as this study was not designed to assess this.

For the reader

- The results of this study should not be interpreted as 'no effect' because the study was not large enough to rule out important treatment benefits or harms.

Minor points

- Given the open-label design of this study, it is important to consider if usual antiviral treatment varied between arms, but this information is not presented.
- There is a difference between one of the primary outcome measures described on the trial registry and those reported in the trial paper – *time to SARS-CoV-2 negativity* has been switched for *percentage of subjects who were SARS-CoV-2 negative by day 14*. One purpose of a trial registry is to avoid the risk of false conclusions due to selective outcome reporting, and although that is unlikely to be the case here, it is important to stick rigidly to any pre-specified methods or justify deviations fully. Mortality at 28 days and time to treatment failure were listed as secondary outcomes but not reported.
- Time to event outcomes have been included, such as *time to clinical improvement* and *time to SARS-CoV-2 negativity*. With these outcomes there is a possibility of censoring, where participants leave the study before the event of interest happened. Kaplan-Meier curves and associated analyses are recommended for this type of data, because they allow for censoring and lead to correct calculations of median time to event (though in this case, the only patient that was censored appears to be the one that was excluded because they stopped taking favipiravir).
- While the study was open-label, it is not clear if the outcome assessments were blinded.
- There is little information on how the randomisation sequence was generated. The authors did not note any methods for restricting the randomization, but the allocation was still perfectly balanced with 10 patients in each arm.
- Presentation of graphs could be improved by using clear labels for axes and legends.

Open Data

Not reported

Open Analysis Code

None provided

Pre-registered study design

Yes

PubPeer

There are currently no comments on the PubPeer page for the published version of this paper.

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/2DA9CCF76E04DAA4709642BF1D06A7>

References

1. MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership.
<https://www.methodologyhubs.mrc.ac.uk/about/tmrp/>.
2. Lou, Y., Liu, L. & Qiu, Y. *Clinical Outcomes and Plasma Concentrations of Baloxavir Marboxil and Favipiravir in COVID-19 Patients: an Exploratory Randomized, Controlled Trial*.
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doi:10.1101/2020.04.29.20085761.
3. Schulz, K. F., Altman, D. G., Moher, D. & for the CONSORT Group. CONSORT 2010 Statement: updated guidelines for reporting parallel group randomised trials. *BMJ* **340**, c332–c332 (2010).

CONSORT CHECKLIST

To support the review, we completed the CONSORT checklist³ below. Material taken directly from the paper (or trial registry) is in *italics*. Our additional comments are in **bold**.

Title and abstract

1a Identification as a randomised trial in the title

Yes

1b Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions.

Title: Identification of the study as randomised	Yes
Authors: Contact details for the corresponding author	Yes
Trial design: Description of the trial design (eg, parallel, cluster, non-inferiority)	Yes
Methods	
Participants: Eligibility criteria for participants and the settings where the data were collected	Yes
Interventions: Interventions intended for each group	Yes
Objective: Specific objective or hypothesis	Yes
Outcome: Clearly defined primary outcome for this report	Yes
Randomisation: How participants were allocated to interventions	Yes
Blinding (masking): Whether or not participants, care givers, and those assessing the outcomes were blinded to group assignment	Partially
Results	
Numbers randomised: Number of participants randomised to each group	Yes
Recruitment: Trial status	Partially
Numbers analysed: Number of participants analysed in each group	Yes
Outcome: For the primary outcome, a result for each group and the estimated effect size and its precision	No
Harms: Important adverse events or side-effects	Yes
Conclusions: General interpretation of the results	Yes
Trial registration: Registration number and name of trial register	Yes
Funding: Source of funding	Yes

Introduction

Background and objectives

2a Scientific background and explanation of rationale

The latest data shows that some antiviral drugs, including favipiravir, remdesivir, chloroquine phosphate, have inhibitory effect against SARS-CoV-2 in vitro[2]. However, due to the limited clinical experience of using these drugs in COVID-19 patients, inadequate understanding of their mechanism of action against SARS-CoV-2, the antiviral drugs currently in use need more in-depth research basis in clinical application for COVID-19, and their potential efficacy against the SARS-CoV-2 virus has been controversial.

2b Specific objectives or hypotheses

This study aims to evaluate the clinical outcomes and plasma concentrations of baloxavir marboxil and favipiravir in COVID-19 patients.

Methods

Trial design

3a Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio

This trial was an exploratory single center, open-label, randomized, controlled trial.

Participants confirmed as COVID-19 infection were randomly allocated (1:1:1) to the study after approval by the ethics committees

3b Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons

None reported

Participants

4a Eligibility criteria for participants

The selected subjects must meet all of the following inclusion criteria: (1) Adults 18-85 years of age, either man or woman, who have signed the informed consent voluntarily; (2) Confirmed as COVID-19: positive results of throat swab or blood samples by real-time RT-PCR assay for 2019-nCoV; (3) No difficulty in swallowing oral drugs; (4) Ability to follow the protocol according to the judgment of researchers. Subjects must be excluded if they meet any of the following

criteria: (1) Allergic constitution, known to be allergic to baloxavir marboxil or favipiravir or pharmaceutical excipients; (2) Weight < 40 kg; (3) Critical illness meeting one of the following conditions: respiratory failure and mechanical ventilation; shock; other organ failure requiring ICU monitoring and treatment; (4) Renal insufficiency (estimated creatinine clearance < 60 ml/min); (5) With any of the following laboratory parameter abnormalities detected within 24 hours before screening(according to local laboratory reference range): ALT or AST level > 5 times the upper limit of normal range (ULN) , or ALT or AST level > 3-fold ULN and total bilirubin level > 2-fold ULN; (6) Base on the researcher's judgment, there are other factors that may cause the subject to be forced to terminate the study midway, such as other serious diseases, serious laboratory examination abnormalities, other factors that affect the safety of the subject or study data and blood sample collection.

4b Settings and locations where the data were collected

The trial was initiated on February 3, 2020, and the data were collected in The First Affiliated Hospital, Zhejiang University School of Medicine.

Interventions

5 The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered

All patients start the recommended antiviral treatment (lopinavir/ritonavir, darunavir/cobicistat or arbidol, described below) immediately after the admission diagnosis and received standard care. The trial treatment scheme started as soon as consent was obtained (Day 1). The specific administration is as follows: (1) Baloxavir marboxil group: baloxavir marboxil is used in combination with the existing antiviral treatment (described below). The dose was 80 mg once a day orally on Day 1 and Day 4; for patients who are still positive in virological test, they can be given again on Day 7, no more than three additional doses; (2) Favipiravir group: favipiravir was used in combination with the existing antiviral treatment. The first dose was 1600 mg or 2200mg orally, followed by 600 mg each time, three times a day, and the duration of administration was not more than 14 days; (3) Control group: Continue the existing antiviral treatment. The existing antiviral treatment included lopinavir/ritonavir (400mg/100mg, bid, po.) or darunavir/cobicistat (800mg/150mg, qd, po.) and arbidol (200mg, tid, po.). All of them were used in combination with interferon inhalation (100,000 iu, tid or qid).

Outcomes

6a Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed

The primary efficacy end point was the percentage of subjects with viral negative by Day 14 and the time from randomization to clinical improvement, defined as the time from randomization to an improvement of two points (from the status at randomization) on a seven-category ordinal

scale or live discharge from the hospital, whichever came first. The ordinal scale, which is refer to National Early Warning Score 2 (NEWS2), have been used as end points in clinical trials in patients hospitalized with COVID-19. Secondary clinical end points included the percentage of subjects with viral negative by Day 7, the incidence of mechanical ventilation by Day 14, ICU admission by Day 14, and all-cause mortality by Day14.

6b Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons

Not reported. Note some difference to outcomes in trial registry.

Sample size

7a How sample size was determined

Due to the exploratory nature of this study, a formal sample size calculation would have been of little value and therefore it was not performed.

7b When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines

N/A

Randomisation

Sequence generation

8a Method used to generate the random allocation sequence

SAS software was used to generate the random number and the treatment group corresponding to the random number.

8b Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)

Not reported. From above simple randomisation could be assumed.

Allocation concealment mechanism

9 Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned

After the subjects passed screening, the researchers assigned the random number according to the order of enrollment, removed the random envelope according to the random number, and treated the subjects according to the random envelope group and treatment plan.

Partially reported. Were envelopes opaque, sealed, sequentially ordered?

Implementation

10 Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions

Not reported

Blinding

11a If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how

The blind method is not suitable for this trial.

Only partially reported. Consider participants, caregivers and outcome assessors.

11b If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions

Statistical methods

12a Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes

Due to the exploratory nature of this study, a formal sample size calculation would have been of little value and therefore it was not performed. Similarly, more statistical analysis will not be performed

12b Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses

Results

Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)

13a For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome

Fig 1

13b For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons

Fig 1.

Reasons not all reported.

Recruitment

14a Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up

The trial was initiated on February 3, 2020, and the data were collected in The First Affiliated Hospital, Zhejiang University School of Medicine.

End date not reported.

14b Why the trial ended or was stopped

N/A

Baseline data

15 A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group

Table 1

Numbers analysed

16 For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups

Figure 1

Outcomes and estimation

17a For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)

Table 2.

Precision and effect size not reported.

17b For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended

Ancillary analyses

18 Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted

analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory

Harms

19 All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms⁴²)

Table 4

Discussion

Limitations

20 Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses

One reason for the lack of virological effect and clinical benefits may be due to insufficient concentrations of these drugs relative to their antiviral activities.

Generalisability

21 Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings

Interpretation

22 Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence

Our findings do not support that adding either baloxavir or favipiravir under the trial dosages to the existing standard treatment.

Other information

Registration

23 Registration number and name of trial registry

The trial was registered with Chinese Clinical Trial Registry (ChiCTR 2000029544).

Protocol

24 Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available

Not reported

Funding

25 Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders

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